

IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA USE ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Introduction

Social media is used by billions of people across the world for various reasons. Likewise, Sri Lanka has also been hit by the social media phenomenon. The majority of social media users are the youth in colleges and universities (Hussain 2012). Due to the increase in the popularity of social media among university students, several researchers have focused on whether the academic performance of students is being affected by the extensive use of these social media.

In empirical researches on social media, many significant negative impacts on students' academic performance have been identified (Cao & Hong 2011). Among those studies, Kirschner and Karpinski (2010) found that Facebook users who are spending lesser time on their studies resulted with low GPA when compared to non-Facebook users. Similarly, a study carried out using 450 undergraduates of the University for Development Studies in Ghana have found that the academic performance of the students is being affected negatively due to various reasons, the major reason among them was the distraction resulted by social media during lectures (Tuurosong & Faisal 2014).

Conversely, positive contributions are also identified by previous researchers. They found that the usage of social media enhances the potential of students to outstanding in academic success through connecting to educational networks and collaborative learning by interacting with peers (Habes et al. 2018). Similarly, in a quantitative research study carried out to determine the effect of growing use of social media sites on Pakistan students' academic performance found that the students can share and generate new ideas and concepts relating to their studies using social media sites hence their academic performance is positively affected (Amin *et al.* 2016). However, prior studies did not focus on the impact of social media on academic performance through collaborative learning in the Sri Lankan

context. This study fills that gap by identifying the impact of using social media on the academic performance of Sri Lankan undergraduates through collaborative learning.

Methodology

A conceptual model developed by Al-Rahmi and Othman (2013) was used for this study, which examined the impact of social media use on academic performance through collaborative learning (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of the Study

The study used a quantitative approach using a cross-sectional questionnaire survey. The population identified in this study is the undergraduates of Sri Lanka, thus a self-administrated questionnaire with 7-point Likert scale questions was randomly distributed among three leading state universities in Sri Lanka. The questionnaire contained questions to measure their interactivity with peers, interactivity with teachers, engagement, collaborative learning when using social media and their academic performance. We received only 100 responses from the questionnaire survey. Based on the nature of the model, data analysis was performed using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) technique with Smart PLS software. Four hypotheses were tested using the path analysis to test the model. MS Excel was also used for descriptive data analysis.

Results and Discussion

The popularity of different social media applications among the respondents was analysed (Figure 2) using collected data. Based on the result, all the respondents used WhatsApp. Facebook and YouTube usage of the respondents were 96% and 93% respectively.

The reliability and the validity of the conceptual model were evaluated before the model testing.

Figure 2: Popularity of different social media applications

The composite reliability above the 0.7 threshold value signifying the constructs produce similar results under consistent condition (Wong 2013). The convergent validity of the constructs measured through the average variance extracted (AVE) above the 0.5 threshold value confirmed the convergence of the items that measure each of the constructs in the model (Wong 2013). Further, the discriminant validity of the constructs was also confirmed as the square root of the AVE of each construct was larger than the latent variable correlation of the constructs. Validity analysis also confirmed that the variables used in the research are acceptable as it is without any modifications.

The relationships between the constructs in the model were evaluated through path coefficients and related *t* statistics which were produced in Smart PLS bootstrapping process with re-sampling technique. The assessment of the structural model revealed that three out of four hypotheses can be accepted (Table 1).

Table 1: Significance testing result of the structural model path coefficients

Hypotheses	Path	Path Coefficient	t-Statistics	Result
H1	Interactivity with peers -> Collaborative learning	0.215	2.553**	ACCEPTED
H2	Interactivity with teachers -> Collaborative learning	0.049	0.493**	REJECTED
H3	Engagement -> Collaborative learning	0.572	6.282*****	ACCEPTED
H4	Collaborative learning -> Students academic performance	0.727	17.062*****	ACCEPTED

Notes: ***** $P < 0.001$, *** $P < 0.01$, ** $P < 0.05$

The path coefficients and their respective *t*-statistics manifested the strength of each hypothesized relationship. There is a positive and significant relationship between interactivity with peers using social media and collaborative learning. Reflecting that interactivity with peers has a weak significant positive impact on collaborative learning. In addition to that, there is a positive but non-significant relationship between the interactivity with teachers using social media and collaborative learning ($p < 0.05$ level with a path coefficient of 0.049). This indicated that Interactivity with teachers using social media has a non-significant impact on collaborative learning. The results have shown both the relationships engagement using social media and Collaborative learning; collaborative learning and students' academic performance has a strong positive relationship. Based on the overall analysis it was also noted that collaborative learning is strongly influenced by engagement of undergraduates on academic activities through social media since the H3 hypothesis shows the highest path coefficient value among other hypotheses.

When reviewing the predictability of the model, it was found that 56.7 % of collaborative learning of students can be predicted by the students' Interactivity with peers, Interactivity with teachers and Engagement in studies. Furthermore, the analysis revealed that 52.8% of the academic performance of students can be predicted by their level of collaborative learning.

Conclusion

This research was mainly conducted to test a conceptual model identified through the literature on the impact of student's collaborative learning with the support of social media on academic performance. The model comprised of five constructs namely, Interaction with peers using social media, interaction with teachers using social media, engagement of students, collaborative learning and students' academic performance. The model was tested using the data collected from a sample of 100 undergraduates from three leading state universities in Sri Lanka using a questionnaire structured with 7-point Likert scale questions to measure the five constructs in the conceptual model.

Based on the analysis it was found that interaction with peers using social media and engagement of students has a significant impact on collaborative learning of students and also it has a significant impact on students' academic performance in the context of Sri Lanka. The student's interaction with teachers using social media has no significant impact on students' collaborative learning. Results of this study show that almost every undergraduate in the sample uses social media platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp and Viber for interacting with colleagues. However, when considering the use of social media for collaborative learning, the student's interaction with their lecturers seems to be non-significant. When it comes to the Sri Lankan context, there may be several reasons behind the students' less use of social media to communicate with lecturers. According to the researchers' opinion, one of the causes can be students are hesitant to reveal their private lives to their lecturers and as a result, they are reluctant to communicate with them using social media. Another reason behind maybe, once students and lecturers connect using social media there is a greater possibility of crossing student-lecturer professional boundaries and both lecturers and students are not willing to cross these boundaries and as a result, they expect less to communicate with each other through social media.

Given these points, university students should identify and analyse the effect of extensive social media on academic performance and identify ways to get the maximum out of the time spent on social media towards their academic achievements.

There were several limitations which came into consideration when finalizing this study. The main limitation identified is, the limitations related to the sample which the researcher has selected. Although the objective of the study is to identify the impact of social media usage on academic performance of university students through collaborative learning in the Sri Lankan Context, the researcher collected the data using convenience random samples and it confined to undergraduate students of selected three leading state universities in Sri Lanka. Therefore, the data and findings may not be representative of the whole Sri Lankan context. For future research work, it is recommended to use a larger sample covering more from the population which represents the students in Sri Lanka.

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